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Tiberian Pseudo Medallions of the
CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) Group
and the Problem of Chronology

by

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Tiberian Pseudo Medallions of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) Group and the Problem of Chronology¹

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[PLATE 15]

A FEW YEARS AGO, Peter Mittag published a useful catalogue of Roman ‘medallions’ up to Hadrian.² Attention to terminology, however: since imperial bronze medallions proper were struck in quantity only from Hadrian onwards, the bulk of the pre-Hadrianic material listed by Mittag in fact falls into the category of ‘pseudo medallions’, according to J.M.C. Toynbee’s classification – a classification currently widely accepted, and with good reason. As per Toynbee, pseudo medallions are specimens struck from coin dies, but lifted ‘out of the category of coins into that of medals’.³ Among such ‘medallised coins’, Toynbee fittingly distinguished various sub-groups: the most important one comprises pieces struck on large flans, for example sestertius flans struck with dies carved for middle bronzes, or medallion flans, sometimes grooved around the design, struck with sestertius dies; in German numismatic literature, such pieces are conventionally referred to as ‘Abschläge’. Another sub-group of pseudo medallions is constituted by ordinary coins set into frames of various types.⁴ The purpose of the present contribution is to publish a hitherto unknown Tiberian pseudo medallion, not listed by Mittag, belonging to the first sub-group: it was produced by striking dupondius dies of the famous CLEMENTIAE type on an oversized flan. This piece will be discussed in the context of extremely rare related MODERATIONI(S) specimens, and the implications of the existence of these pseudo medallions for the chronology of the entire group will be explored.

Obv. TI CAESAR DIVI AVG F AVGVST IMP VIII
Laureate head of Tiberius to left. Dotted border.

Rev. CLEMENTIAE in upper field, S–C to left and right of the design
Imago clipeata. Small male bust, frontal, undraped, in the centre of round shield, decorated as follows: around the bust a laurel wreath, surrounded by a thick raised circle of petals, around which there is a border of dots. The outermost rim is decorated with stylised palmettes, which are separated by strokes flanked by dots. Dotted border.

¹ The author’s thanks are due to Gabriella Angeli Bufalini and Maria Cristina Molinari (both Rome), Frank L. Kovacs (Corte Madera, CA) as well as to T.V. Buttrey and W.R. Day (both Cambridge) for their help in preparing this article, and especially to the owner of the specimen presented here for the first time for generously making it available for study.

² P.F. Mittag, *Römische Medaillons. Caesar bis Hadrian* (second ed. Stuttgart, 2012).

³ J.M.C. Toynbee, *Roman Medallions*. With an Introduction to the Reprint Edition by W.E. Metcalf (New York, 1986; first ed. 1944), p. 25.

⁴ Toynbee, *Medallions*, p. 25.

Orichalcum, olive green patina.

Weight 26.64g, die-axis 6h, maximum diameter 35mm.

For the type in general, see *RIC* I (second ed.), Tiberius 38; *BMCRE* I, Tiberius 85–9.

Obverse die: Sutherland A2.⁵ Reverse die: Sutherland P10.⁶ This die-combination is not listed by Sutherland, but attested in the specimen ANS 1944.100.39283 (14.57g, 12h, max. diam. 31mm).

Northern Californian private collection.

Ex Jean Elsen auction 98 (13 December 2008), no. 518 (misidentified).

Pl. 15, figs 1–1a (150%)

The *CLEMENTIAE* dupondii of Tiberius, and their twin-type, the *MODERATIONI(S)* dupondii (*RIC* Tiberius 39f.), are among the most prominent – and certainly most-studied – coin types of the principate of Tiberius struck at the mint of Rome. *Clementia* (‘mercy’) and *moderatio* (‘temperance’), frequently found coupled in the literary sources, were key virtues of Roman rulers since Julius Caesar,⁷ for whose self-fashioning especially *clementia* played a fundamental role.⁸ Both *clementia* and *moderatio* were concepts essential also for Tiberius, as may be gauged from a cursory perusal of historical accounts of his rule.⁹

On their reverses, the *CLEMENTIAE* and *MODERATIONI(S)* coins show two richly decorated round shields, which, though of a similar general appearance, are clearly differentiated between themselves in the details of their ornamentation on almost all the dies of the group. But the centrepiece, the male bust,¹⁰ seems to unite them: there is no obvious differentiation between the two individuals on the two shields/types, although this point should not be pressed, since the busts are extremely small. The one numismatic parallel to these Tiberian *clipeatae imagines* is a shield (decorated with a wreath-design) bearing a (somewhat larger) three-quarter facing, bare-headed, undraped portrait of Augustus in its centre, which is illustrated on denarii struck by the Augustan moneyer L. Mescinius Rufus in 16 BC

⁵ C.H.V. Sutherland, ‘Two “Virtues” of Tiberius: a numismatic contribution to the history of his reign’, *JRS* 28 (1938), pp. 129–40; for the die-study see pp. 133–6, esp. 133f. (this obverse die is attested in multiple examples).

⁶ Sutherland, ‘Two “Virtues”’, p. 135 (this reverse die is attested in the specimen *BMCRE* I, Tiberius 85 = BM, reg. no. R 6363: 17.25g, 12h).

⁷ See Suet. Iul. 75.1: *Moderationem vero clementiamque cum in administratione tum in victoria belli civilis admirabilem exhibuit*. For a definition, see esp. Sen. clem. 2.3.1: *Clementia est temperantia animi in potestate ulciscendi vel lenitas superioris adversus inferiorem in constituendis poenis*. 2: ... *si dixerimus clementiam esse moderationem aliquid ex merita ac debita poena remittentem*.

⁸ See also the denarii *RRC* 480/21 (*CLEMENTIAE CAESARIS*, temple).

⁹ See Suet. Tib. 53.2 (*proque tali clementia interponi decretum passus est* [sc. Tiberius], *quo sibi gratiae agerentur et Capitolino Iovi donum ex auro sacraretur*), Tac. ann. 3.56.1 (*fama moderationis parva*), Tac. ann. 4.74.2 (*aram clementiae ... censuere* [sc. senatores]); see also Vell. Pat. 2.122.1 (*singularis moderatio Ti. Caesaris*). For a lucid analysis of the importance of the two terms to Tiberius, see B. Levick, ‘Mercy and Moderation on the coinage of Tiberius’, in: B. Levick (ed.), *The Ancient Historian and his Materials. Essays in Honour of C.E. Stevens on his Seventieth Birthday* (Farnborough, 1975), pp. 123–37, pp. 123f.

¹⁰ The early modern identification as female busts of the two virtues, for which see I. Eckhel, *Doctrina numorum veterum*, vol. VI: *continens numos imperatorios a Iulio Caesare usque ad Hadrianum eiusque familiam* (Vindobonae, 1796), p. 187, is clearly wrong.

(pl. 15, fig. 5).¹¹ Hence, *a priori* it may seem natural to assume that the individual depicted on the CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI(S) pieces is the emperor himself – he was identified as such without hesitation for example by Harold Mattingly¹² –, and that the coins show dedications to two of his cardinal virtues, his mercy and moderation. However, in an influential paper Helga Gesche proposed to identify the miniature *imagines* on the *clipei* as portraits not of Tiberius, but of Drusus the Younger (the son of Tiberius) and Germanicus, since Tacitus mentions the posthumous award of *clipei* to these two men, while the historian does not say anything about *clipei* for Tiberius.¹³ Still, such an *argumentum ex silentio* based on the fragmentary literary evidence is plainly worthless, and Gesche’s interpretation as a whole is unconvincing, since she has to admit that it would imply that ‘die beiden auf den Dupondien genannten Tugenden, Clementia und Moderatio, haben direkt mit den Ehrenschilden nichts zu tun’.¹⁴ this can hardly be so.

These miniature portraits are certainly difficult to interpret, since their representations show considerable stylistic discrepancies on the various dies. On some of them, roundish heads with childlike features seem in evidence, so that Gesche’s interpretations as portraits of Caesars is to some extent understandable. Still, these may be stylistic aberrations, and one should insist, with Mattingly and C.H.V. Sutherland, on the fact that the longish head on one excellent CLEMENTIAE die allows for an identification with the emperor himself without problems.¹⁵ On balance, the *imagines* were probably intended to depict Tiberius himself, two of whose principate’s core values were celebrated by the dedication of the shields pictured on the coins.

In what must be one of the earliest die-studies of a Roman imperial coin issue ever, Humphrey Sutherland demonstrated in 1938 that the CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI(S) dupondii were die-linked through their obverses, and that they formed a rather restricted, yet tightly-knit group, for which Sutherland could document 8 obverse and 16 reverse dies.¹⁶ The eighth imperial acclamation of Tiberius, cited on the obverse of these coins, is the only chronological anchor their

¹¹ *RIC* I (second ed.), Augustus 356–7. On these coins see the discussion by A. Küter, *Zwischen Republik und Kaiserzeit. Die Münzmeisterprägung unter Augustus*. Berliner Numismatische Forschungen, Neue Folge 11 (Berlin, 2014), pp. 190–4. This *clipeus* is accompanied by the dedicatory legend S(enatus) C(onsulto) OB R(em) P(ublicam) CVM SALVT(e) IMP(eratoris) CAESAR(is) AVGVS(ti) CONS(ervatam).

¹² *BMCRE* I, pp. cxxxvi and 132.

¹³ H. Gesche, ‘Datierung und Deutung der CLEMENTIAE–MODERATIONI–Dupondien des Tiberius’, *JNG* 21 (1971), pp. 37–80, pp. 55f.: Tac. ann. 2.83.3 (Germanicus) and 4.9.2 (Drusus the Younger). The idea that the tiny *imagines* on the *clipei* depict not Tiberius, but either these two men or the elder sons of Germanicus was also expressed by Levick, ‘Mercy and Moderation’, pp. 132f.

¹⁴ Gesche, ‘Datierung und Deutung’, p. 61.

¹⁵ See C.H.V. Sutherland, ‘The *Clementiae* and *Moderationi* dupondii of Tiberius: more thoughts on the chronology’, *NC* 139 (1979), pp. 21–5, p. 24 and esp. pl. 3, no. 6. This is an enlargement of the bust on the CLEMENTIAE specimen *BMCRE* Tiberius 87 (Mattingly: ‘distinct features of Tiberius visible’). The die is the reverse die Sutherland, ‘Two “Virtues”’, P2. The statement by Levick, ‘Mercy and Moderation’, p. 132 that the person depicted was ‘well endowed with hair, unlike the Princeps’ is not to the point.

¹⁶ Sutherland, ‘Two “Virtues”’, p. 136.

inscriptions provide. Unfortunately, it yields just a very rough dating, from AD 16 to the death of Tiberius in AD 37: the eighth acclamation was the emperor's last.¹⁷ Accordingly, the dates proposed for the group in scholarship vary considerably, from the 'early dating' AD 16¹⁸ to the 'middle dating' AD 22/3¹⁹ and the 'late dating' AD 34–7.²⁰

In general, this author fully subscribes to Mattingly's and Sutherland's conclusion that the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) bronzes cannot have been struck in the latest phase of the principate of Tiberius, mainly on stylistic grounds: the portraits of Tiberius on the obverses are partly of exquisite style and would not fit with the late groups of Tiberian middle bronzes; the piece described above, published here for the first time, is a good example of this. Also, our coins celebrating the emperor's mercy and temperance seem to be associated thematically with the beautiful bronze issues – also dupondii – depicting IVSTITIA, PIETAS and SALVS AVGVSTA, all dated to AD 22/3 through the *tribuniciae potestates* of Tiberius and his son Drusus.²¹ Hence, the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) group probably should not have been struck after AD 22/3.²² However, there is more to be said about the dating of these coins, on the basis of the numismatic evidence assembled here, so we shall return to the chronological problem below.

But first some technical comments on our new pseudo medallion: at 26.64g, the orichalcum flan used for this piece must of course have been a sestertius flan;²³ the weights of the six CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI dupondii published in *BMCRE I* are merely between 12.54 and 17.25g. As mentioned above, a pseudo medallion of the CLEMENTIAE type was unknown to Mittag, but our piece fits well with the material he presents. His book makes it possible to follow the development of pseudo medallions from reign to reign, which allows for important structural observations. While under Augustus a good number of (putative) presentation pieces struck by the moneyers at the mint of Rome in bronze on oversize flans, decorated

¹⁷ On the date of this acclamation (the only one Tiberius received as a sole ruler), see D. Kienast – W. Eck – M. Heil, *Römische Kaisertabelle. Grundzüge einer römischen Kaiserchronologie. 6., überarbeitete Auflage* (Darmstadt, 2017), pp. 72f. (late summer AD 16). It is recorded by Tac. ann. 2.18.2; see also Levick, 'Mercy and Moderation', p. 136, note 53 (with bibliography).

¹⁸ Thus Levick, 'Mercy and Moderation', p. 132.

¹⁹ Thus Mattingly in *BMCRE I*, p. 132, note *, and Sutherland, 'Two "Virtues"', p. 140. See also Sutherland, 'The *Clementiae* and *Moderationi* dupondii', p. 24. For further remarks on the series by C.H.V. Sutherland, cp. *Coinage in Roman Imperial Policy 31 B.C.–A.D. 68* (London, 1951), pp. 97–9 and 193f., as well as *The Emperor and the Coinage. Julio-Claudian Studies* (London, 1976), pp. 110f.

²⁰ Thus H. Gesche, 'Datierung und Deutung', p. 48; followed e.g. by W. Szaivert, *Die Münzprägung der Kaiser Tiberius und Caius (Caligula) 14/41. Moneta Imperii Romani 2 and 3* (Vienna, 1984), pp. 30, 35, 37 and 57 (AD 34/5). A late dating is also advocated by A. Biasoli, 'Osservazioni su due originali monete di Tiberio', *QT 6* (1977), pp. 177–88, and J.-B. Giard, *Bibliothèque nationale. Catalogue des monnaies de l'empire romain*, vol. II. *De Tibère à Neron* (Paris, 1988) [henceforward *BNCMER II*], p. 24.

²¹ See *RIC I* (second ed.), Tiberius 43 (Drusus TR P II, AD 23), 46 and 47 (Tiberius, TR P XXVIII, AD 22/3).

²² See Mattingly in *BMCRE I*, p. 132, note: 'Assigned to this year [sc. AD 22/3] on convincing grounds of style'. Cp. also Sutherland, 'The *Clementiae* and *Moderationi* dupondii', p. 23.

²³ Mattingly calculated 27.04g as the average weight of Tiberian sestertii (*BMCRE I*, p. liv); Sutherland gives 25.50–28.25g as their principal weight range (*RIC I*, second ed., p. 90).

with characteristic, sometimes concentric grooves around the design, is attested,²⁴ such grooved pieces are conspicuous by their virtual absence under Tiberius. During the rule of the second *princeps*, pseudo medallions were more modest in appearance and almost exclusively took the shape of pieces struck on plain flans bigger than required for the denominations the dies were originally intended for.²⁵

Peter Mittag chose to split the catalogue of the Tiberian pseudo medallions known to him in two: while cataloguing two particularly weighty DIVVS AVGVSTVS PATER pieces of 43.49g and 58.81g respectively in the main catalogue as “Tib I–2”,²⁶ he relegated twelve types on large (but somewhat less heavy) flans – mostly middle bronze dies struck on sestertius flans – into a sort of appendix (“Tib I–XII”),²⁷ which is partly in need of revision.²⁸ The division in two parts in Mittag’s catalogue perhaps makes sense in a practical perspective, yet it seems questionable methodologically, not only since the Divus Augustus types represented on very heavy flans turn up in both parts of the catalogue: the phenomenon of strikes on large flans clearly needs to be viewed as a whole. Mittag’s tentative suggestion that the Roman mint may have used sestertius flans instead of middle bronze planchets by mistake, in these cases under Tiberius,²⁹ is hardly convincing for at least two reasons. Firstly, there are instances catalogued by Mittag in which dies intended for asses were struck on sestertius flans – the marked difference in colour between the golden orichalcum of the planchet that was used and the red copper of the flan that would have been appropriate for the denomination, combined with the different module, makes a blunder on the part of the mint workers implausible here.³⁰ Secondly, the suggestion that these strikes are “Fehlprägungen” is unlikely in view of the relatively high incidence of “error coins” of this type – Mittag’s catalogue (which might be expanded) comprises no fewer than fourteen specimens: to sum up, the large planchets should certainly have

²⁴ See Mittag, *Medaillons*, pp. 26ff. and pls 2–5.

²⁵ On this phenomenon, see already the remark by Mattingly, *BMCRE* I, p. cxxxi. The one exception is the enigmatic and atypical composite piece Mittag “Tib 3” which I do not consider here.

²⁶ Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 121.

²⁷ Mittag, *Medaillons*, pp. 192–4.

²⁸ For example, the type “Tib VIII” (DIVVS AVGVSTVS PATER, rev. Victory to the left with shield SPQR) is not in the British Museum as indicated (the specimen referenced by Mittag, *BMCRE* Tiberius 141, is of ordinary module). For a specimen of this type on a sestertius flan, see, however, Jacob Hirsch 24 (10 May 1909: Consul Weber, part two), no. 842 = *Ars Classica* 18 (10 October 1938: diplomate étranger [de Sartiges]), no. 48 (25.67g). Another specimen of the type Mittag “Tib VII” (DIVVS AVGVSTVS PATER, rev. temple of Vesta) on a sestertius flan is in Berlin: ex Sandes coll., acquired in 1879 (23.58g, 7h, 37mm), see <<http://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18208035>>. For a further addition, see below in the text. The generic reference to a DIVVS AVGVSTVS PATER piece on a heavy flan in the Milan collection, given twice by Mittag (pp. 121 and 194), after *RIC* I (second ed.), p. 99, nos 82–3 note, may be specified as follows: *Comune di Milano. Catalogo delle raccolte numismatiche*. Vol. I: *Le monete dell’impero da Augusto a Traiano* (Milan, 1938), p. 54, no. 540 = R. Martini, *Sylloge Nummorum Romanorum Italia. Milano, Civiche Raccolte Numismatiche*. Vol. 1: *Giulio-Claudii*. Part 1: Augustus–Tiberius (Milan, 1990), no. 271 (28.82g; 34.5mm). The piece is holed, its reverse illegible; it may even be a uniface strike.

²⁹ Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 32 (“Hier ist ein Versehen nicht auszuschließen”); cp. also p. 33.

³⁰ See Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 193, “Tib V” (Giard, *BNCMER* II, Tibère no. 108) and p. 194, “Tib. XI” (= Giard, *BNCMER* II, Tibère no. 140).

been used by design. As for the function of all these Tiberian pieces, no definite conclusion seems possible. Pseudo-medallic strikes on sestertius flans certainly could circulate as coins of the latter denomination, but nevertheless a primary function as presentation pieces seems to suggest itself.

Among the coins relegated to the second part of Mittag's catalogue we find one specimen of a MODERATIONIS piece struck on a large sestertius flan in the Paris collection, where a disproportionately high percentage of such oversize strikes is kept (Mittag "Tib I": 24.97g, 6h; **pl. 15, fig. 2**):³¹ this specimen evidently is a counterpart of the CLEMENTIAE piece published here. However, another pertinent example from a different reverse die may be added: a MODERATIONI piece on a sestertius flan in the Florence coin cabinet, first described in print as being in that collection in 1868 (25.18g, 12h, max. diameter 34mm; **pl. 15, fig. 3**).³² This specimen was struck from the same obverse die as the CLEMENTIAE piece presented here for the first time.

Hence, we are currently able to document three strikes of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) group on sestertius flans: two in public museums and one in a private collection. The individual weights of these three pieces are 24.97g, 25.18g and 26.64g respectively.³³ In 1892, Francesco Gnecci published an overview article of Roman bronze strikes on oversized flans, in which he also listed – but unfortunately did not illustrate – a MODERATIONI specimen in his own collection ("Coll. Gnecci a Milano").³⁴ Since a pseudo medallion of this kind currently is not kept among Gnecci's coins in the coin cabinet of the Museo Nazionale Romano

³¹ Giard, *BNCMER II*, Tibère no. 130 (inv. AF 936A, H. 1602). Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 192 erroneously gives the legend as MODERATIONI.

³² Editio princeps: C. Strozzi, 'Medaglie imperiali della collezione delle RR. Gallerie di Firenze, non descritte da Cohen', *Periodico di Numismatica e Sfragistica per la Storia d'Italia* 1 (1868), pp. 11–6, p. 16, no. 12 (with drawing on pl. I, no. 7). Subsequently published (with a photo) by A. Banti – L. Simonetti, *Corpus Nummorum Romanorum*. Vol. IX: *Tiberio. Monete d'oro, d'argento, di bronzo e coloniali, con 1170 illustrazioni* (Florence, 1976), pp. 144f., no. 257; now see F. Catalli – B. Spigola, *Sylloge Nummorum Romanorum Italia. Firenze, Monetaire del Museo Archeologico Nazionale*. Vol. II: *Tiberius Claudius Nero (14–37 d.C.), Caius Caesar Germanicus (37–41 d.C.), Tiberius Claudius Nero Germanicus (41–54 d.C.)* (Florence – Pavia, 2014), p. 24, no. 54.

³³ Robert Mowat twice published a CLEMENTIAE dupondius kept in the Paris collection as being a "grand bronze" (or pseudo medallion), but his contention should be disregarded: he refers to the specimen Giard, *BNCMER II*, p. 53, no. 125, which – it is true – is struck on a somewhat broader, oblong flan, but weighs only 16.51g and consequently does not belong to the group struck on sestertius flans isolated here. See R. Mowat, 'Contributions à la théorie des médaillons de bronze romains. Fabrication des médaillons à deux métaux', *RIN* 24 (1911), pp. 165–84, p. 176, no. 13 (inv. "grands bronzes 918" = Giard no. 125) = R. Mowat, 'Bronzes remarquables de Tibère, de son fils, de ses petits-fils et de Caligula', *RN*, quatrième série 15 (1911), pp. 335–51, p. 335, no. 1. Incidentally, this specimen may have contributed to inspiring the following statement by H. Cohen, *Description historique des monnaies de l'empire romain*, second ed., vol. 1 (Paris, 1880), p. 190, note 1: "le fait est que les médailles à ces deux types [sc. CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI(S)] sont souvent d'un module qui excède un peu le moyen bronze ordinaire."

³⁴ F. Gnecci, '[Appunti di numismatica romana.] XXV. Il medaglione senatorio. Saggio di una prima serie', *RIN* 5 (1892), pp. 291–316, p. 298, no. 5. In the description of the reverse, Gnecci writes "Busto della Clemenza", but his reference to Cohen confirms that he is indeed describing a MODERATIONI piece.

in Rome,³⁵ it may be presumed that Gneccchi parted with it in or after 1892. It is impossible to be sure about its fate, on the information currently available. Still, given the rarity of such pieces it does not seem too frivolous to point out that the weight of the piece given by Gneccchi in his article – exactly 25g – is very close to the weight of the Paris specimen mentioned above (24.97g), which was accessioned at the French national collection only in 1906.³⁶ Of course, if one wanted to identify the Paris specimen as ex-Gneccchi, one would have to accuse the illustrious collector of mistranscribing the reverse legend of his own coin in print – MODERATIONI, whereas the piece now in Paris in fact reads MODERATIONIS –, but then he seems to have written the passage in question somewhat carelessly anyway.³⁷ *Non liquet*.

The existence of at least three CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI(S) strikes on what are doubtless sestertius flans should be taken to indicate that this entire group of coins was produced at the Roman mint at a time when sestertii were being struck there, too: it seems unlikely in the extreme that flans precisely of sestertius module should have been produced specifically for our rare pseudo medallions during a period when they were not needed for a regular coinage. This consideration allows us to disprove the early dating of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) coins to AD 16, advocated by Barbara Levick³⁸ and – unlike the ‘late dating’ – not firmly rejected by Sutherland, who assigned this group to “c. AD 16–22” in the catalogue section of *RIC*.³⁹ This is obviously incorrect. No ordinary sestertii were struck during the first eight years of the principate of Tiberius, from AD 14 to early AD 22;⁴⁰ sestertius production in Tiberius’ rule set in only with the issue dated to the emperor’s *tribunicia potestas* XXIII, hence to the period 26 June AD 22 to 25 June AD 23.⁴¹ This resumption of the striking of the largest brass denomination of the Augustan system was a significant event, since no sestertii had been struck at the mint of Rome at all since the issues of the Augustan moneyers Sanquinius, Licinius Stolo and Sempronius Gracchus in 17 BC⁴² – in other words, there had been a hiatus of forty years. After the Tiberian sestertius issue dated TR P XXIII, sestertius production lapsed again for twelve years, until the issue of AD 34/5 (TR P XXXVI). Since such a late dating of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) coins may safely be excluded, as laid out above, this means that the group should have been produced not before – and probably in connection with – the large Tiberian bronze issue of AD 22/3. Hence, the dating of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) pieces originally proposed by Harold Mattingly in *BMCRE* I should stand.

³⁵ My sincere thanks to Gabriella Angeli Bufalini (Rome) for kindly checking this at my request.

³⁶ Giard, *BNCMER* II, p. 54, no. 130 note: “Legs Torey 1906”.

³⁷ On this, see note 34 above and Banti – Simonetti, *Tiberio*, p. 145.

³⁸ ‘Mercy and Moderation’, p. 132.

³⁹ *RIC* I (second ed.), p. 97.

⁴⁰ The one possible exception being the large DIVVS AVGVSTVS PATER bronzes *RIC* I (second ed.), Tiberius 70 (two specimens known: Copenhagen and ANS 1979.11.1), although their denomination and date are completely uncertain. The ANS specimen has a reddish tone.

⁴¹ *RIC* I (second ed.), Tiberius 42ff.; *BMCRE* I, p. cxxxii; Szaivert, *Münzprägung*, pp. 30, 35 and 56.

⁴² Mattingly, *BMCRE* I, p. xcvi; Küter, *Zwischen Republik und Kaiserzeit*, p. 24.

Appendix

Pseudo Medallions of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) Group in Early Modern Numismatic Scholarship

Considering the extremely reduced number of pseudo medallions on sestertius flans of our group known today, it seems remarkable that CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI specimens were listed not only as middle bronzes, but also among coin types “ex aere magno” already in the numismatic literature of the eighteenth century: for example in the *Thesaurus Morellianus*, a three-volume compendium of 1752, summing up much of the previous scholarly research on early imperial coins.⁴³ While most of the references for these large strikes to works of the ‘Old Masters’ of numismatic studies given in the *Thesaurus* are not very helpful, from today’s point of view, one is crucial. In Jean Vaillant’s catalogue of important Roman imperial coins, the first edition of which, published in 1674, is the most valuable in scholarly terms,⁴⁴ specimens of sestertius size⁴⁵ of both of the types we are dealing with are listed (though not illustrated), and the respective collections in which Vaillant saw the pieces are noted.

Vaillant recorded the MODERATIONI type “in Cimmelio Emin. Card. Buoncompagni”, that is to say in the collection of Cardinal Girolamo Boncompagni (1622–84), Archbishop of Bologna, who had inherited the collection of his uncle, Cardinal Francesco Boncompagni (1596–1644).⁴⁶ A MODERATIONI specimen on a large flan is also described and illustrated in the sumptuous 1742 publication entitled *Nummophylacium Reginae Christinae* (pl. 15, fig. 4)⁴⁷ – a title that is to some extent misleading, as recent research has shown: the plates published in the Hague in 1742 were originally prepared in Rome in the mid-seventeenth century, for

⁴³ *Thesauri Morelliani Tomus Primus* (and *Secundus*), Sive Christ. Schlegelii, Sigeb. Haverkampii, & Antonii Francisci Gorii Commentaria In XII. Priorum Imperatorum Romanorum Numismata Aurea, Argentea, & Aerea, Cujuscunque Moduli, diligentissime conquisita, & ad ipsos Nummos accuratissime delineata, a Celeberrimo Antiquario Andrea Morellio. Vol. 3: *Thesauri Morelliani Tomus Tertius, Continens XII. Priorum Imperatorum Romanorum, a C. J. Caesare ad Domitianum usque, Nec non Augustae Domus Numismata Aurea, Argentea, & Aerea Cujuscunque Moduli, diligentissime conquisita, & ad ipsos Nummos accuratissime delineata a Celeberrimo Antiquario Andrea Morellio* (Amsterdam, 1752). See vol. 1, pp. 574–6, and vol. 3, pl. 87 (“Numism. Tiberii Tab. V”), nos 6–7. Cp. Cohen, *Description historique*, second ed., vol. 1, p. 190, note 1: “Morell donne ces deux revers sur le grand bronze également. Je ne les ai jamais vus”.

⁴⁴ For details on the various editions of the work, see D. Williams – B.E. Woytek, ‘The Rediscovery of a Lost Sestertius Type and the Dacian Embassy to the Roman Senate in AD 102’, *NC* 172 (2012), pp. 47–62, esp. pp. 48f.

⁴⁵ “*Primus modulus*” in the terminology of the day.

⁴⁶ I. Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Praestantiora. A Iulio Caesare ad Postumum et Tyrannos*, 2 vols (Paris: R. de Ninville – I. Villery, 1674). Vol. 1: *De Romanis Aereis seu Senatusconsulto Percussis*, p. 9, see also the “*Index cimeliarchiorum*” on fol. Aa verso. On the Boncompagni coin collection see F. Missere Fontana, ‘Raccolte numismatiche e scambi antiquari a Bologna fra Quattrocento e Seicento. Parte II’, *BollNum* 36–9 (2001–2 [2004]), pp. 207–315, pp. 216–20.

⁴⁷ *Nummophylacium Reginae Christinae, Quod Comprehendit Numismata Aerea Imperatorum Romanorum, Latina, Graeca, atque in Coloniis Cusa, Quondam A Petro Santes Bartolo, Summo Artificio Summaque Fide Incisa Tabulis Aeneis LXIII* (Hagae Comitum, 1742), pl. II, penultimate line (obv. and rev.); described as no. XI on pp. 22f.

a work on Roman imperial and provincial coins to be published by the knowledgeable antiquary of Queen Christina of Sweden, Francesco Gottifredi (?1596–1669) – a work that never made it into print.⁴⁸ While the majority of the coins illustrated on the plates published in 1742 indeed were from the collection of Christina (1626–89), into which Gottifredi’s own collection had been incorporated, others were not,⁴⁹ and consequently we *a priori* cannot be sure where Gottifredi knew the MODERATIONI specimen from. Since such a piece on a large flan is not attested for the queen’s collection (see note 55 below), it is theoretically possible that Gottifredi, who was in contact with Girolamo Boncompagni and was familiar with his collection,⁵⁰ pictured the Boncompagni MODERATIONI specimen (later to be mentioned by Vaillant) on the plate of his projected work. One might be led to speculate further that this very same coin at some point entered the Medici collection: the fate of the Boncompagni coins is unknown,⁵¹ and a MODERATIONI pseudo medallion does not figure in the inventory of the coin collection of Cosimo III de’ Medici (1642–1723) compiled in 1676; hence the specimen now in Florence must have arrived there after that year.⁵² However, a comparison of **figs 3** and **4** shows that the shield on the coin depicted by Gottifredi (**fig. 4**) is decorated with palmettes on its outermost rim, which is highly unusual for MODERATIONI(S) pieces,⁵³ while the shield of the Florence coin (**fig. 3**) displays a wreath at the same position, as almost all the reverse dies of this variety. Consequently, the identity of the piece depicted by Gottifredi must remain unclear; one should perhaps add here that the faithfulness of his engravings concerning typological details is not necessarily above suspicion.

As for the CLEMENTIAE type on a large flan, Vaillant’s entry runs as follows: “*Hic nummus primi moduli, Gazae Christinae Reginae, mole insignis, inter rarissimos computandus est.*”⁵⁴ This extremely rare specimen, recorded by the French numismatist as being in the collection of Christina, Queen of Sweden, unfortunately cannot be identified in the concise catalogue of this collection published after the

⁴⁸ Basic information on the history of the copperplates is provided by B. Woytek, ‘Sigebert Havercamp (1684–1742) als Numismatiker’, in: H. Winter – B. Woytek et al. (eds), *Numismatik und Geldgeschichte im Zeitalter der Aufklärung. Beiträge zum Symposium im Residenzschloss Dresden, 4.–9. Mai 2009* (= NZ 120/121) (Vienna, 2015), pp. 525–97, p. 550f.; on Gottifredi and his work see in greater detail M. C. Molinari, ‘Alcune annotazioni su Francesco Gottifredi («in cuius verba solent iurare antiquarii») e la sua collezione numismatica’, *Rendiconti della Classe di Scienze Morali, Storiche e Filologiche, Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei*, (Serie 9) 15 (2004), pp. 121–54, as well as F. Missere Fontana, *Testimoni parlanti. Le monete antiche a Roma tra Cinquecento e Seicento*. Monete 4 (Rome, 2009), pp. 239–303, esp. 277–91.

⁴⁹ See M. C. Molinari, ‘La collezione numismatica’, in: *Camillo Massimo collezionista di antichità. Fonti e materiali*. Xenia Antiqua. Monografie 3 (Rome, 1996), pp. 159–91, p. 166.

⁵⁰ Missere Fontana, *Testimoni parlanti*, p. 263.

⁵¹ See Missere Fontana ‘Raccolte numismatiche e scambi antiquari a Bologna’, pp. 219f.

⁵² The manuscript: Biblioteca degli Uffizi, Ms. 74, on which see M. C. Molinari (ed.), *Il Forum di Numismatica Antica a Roma Tre. Studi e ricerche sul collezionismo, la circolazione e l’iconografia monetale* (Rome, 2007), p. 12. I am grateful to Maria Cristina Molinari for checking the manuscript for the MODERATIONI piece and sharing her thoughts on this problem with me.

⁵³ Palmettes are encountered only on the MODERATIONIS reverse die Sutherland, ‘Two “Virtues”’, P14 – a die curiously also used for the Paris coin depicted in **fig. 2**.

⁵⁴ Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Praestantiora*, p. 8.

queen's demise by Francesco Cameli;⁵⁵ it does not figure in manuscript inventories of the collection, either,⁵⁶ and it is not depicted on Gottifredi's plates, published in 1742 as *Nummophylacium Reginae Christinae*. A slip by Vaillant? Did he see the specimen in another collection and confuse his notes? That cannot be excluded. In any case, a CLEMENTIAE bronze on a large flan appeared again in 1846 in an auction sale in London, interestingly with a provenance from Rome. It is described – but, yet again, not illustrated – in the *Catalogue of the Greek & Roman Coins, Composing the Truly Valuable Cabinet Formed During the Last Thirty Years by the Cavaliere Campana, of Rome*,⁵⁷ under the heading “Roman, and Colonial, Imperial Medallions, in Bronze”: “this reverse may be presumed unique, and unpublished” (sc. as a medallion).⁵⁸ Whether the CLEMENTIAE specimen on a large flan seen by Jean Vaillant before 1674 later belonged to Campana – and whether this is perhaps the same piece that is now kept in the Northern Californian private collection – we never shall know.

Key to Plate 15:

- 1 *RIC* I (second ed.), Tiberius 38; strike on large flan. Private collection.
- 1a As 1, enlarged to 150%.
- 2 *RIC* I (second ed.), Tiberius 40; strike on large flan. Paris, *BNCMER* II, Tibère no. 130 (inv. AF 936A, H. 1602).
- 3 *RIC* I (second ed.), Tiberius 39; strike on large flan. Florence, *SNR Firenze* II, Tiberius no. 54. Photo F. Catalli.
- 4 *Nummophylacium Reginae Christinae* (1742), pl. II, detail.
- 5 Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett, acc. 1917/187 (3.63g, 2h).
<<http://ww2.smb.museum/ikmk/object.php?id=18202476>>

⁵⁵ *Nummi Antiqui Aurei, Argentei, & Aerei Primae, secundae, seù mediae, minimae, & maximae formae. Latini, Graeci, Consulium, Augustorum, Regum, & Urbium. In Thesauro Christinae Reginae Suecorum &c. Romae Asservati. A Francisco Camelo Eiusdem Maiestatis Antiquario Per Seriem Redacti* (Rome 1690). CLEMENTIAE and MODERATIONI pieces are listed exclusively on p. 59 of the inventory, among the middle bronzes (see p. 54).

⁵⁶ Thanks to Maria Cristina Molinari for checking.

⁵⁷ Sotheby & Co. 23 July 1846 (and following days), p. 42, no. 335.

⁵⁸ The weight of the piece is not given, but its size: “size 12” according to the scale printed on the first page of the catalogue, which corresponds to 40mm. This is about 5mm larger than the diameter of the three specimens of the CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) group on sestertius flans studied here, and one is left wondering if the indication is precise, especially since three other medallions listed on the same page of the Campana auction catalogue are also described as being of “size 12”.

WOYTEK, TIBERIAN PSEUDO MEDALLIONS OF THE CLEMENTIAE/MODERATIONI(S) GROUP

